

The influence of pharmaceutical service quality on outpatient satisfaction levels at the regional general hospital of central buton regency in 2024

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Abstract

Introduction Pharmaceutical services are an important part of the health service system in hospitals because they play a direct role in supporting successful treatment and increasing patient satisfaction.

Research objective to determine the influence of the quality of pharmaceutical services on outpatient satisfaction at the pharmacy installation of Regional Public Hospital of Central Buton Regency in 2024.

Method : This type of research is quantitative research with cross sectional design. The research sample amounted to 100 people. Sampling using purposive sampling method. The research instrument used questionnaire and data analysis was carried out by univariate, bivariate and multivariate analysis.

Results The results of the study showed that the variables of Physical Evidence/Tangible (p-value = 0.015), Reliability (p-value = 0.001), Responsiveness (p-value = 0.001), Assurance (p-value = 0.023), Empathy (p-value = 0.024) and Conformance (p-value = 0.023) which means that there is an influence of Physical Evidence, Reliability, Responsiveness, Assurance, Empathy and Conformance on patient satisfaction.

Conclusion There is an influence of the quality of pharmaceutical services on the satisfaction of outpatients at the Regional Public Hospital of Central Buton Regency.

Keywords: Quality; Pharmaceutical Services; Patient Satisfaction; Servqual Method

1. Introduction

Pharmaceutical services have now shifted their orientation from drugs (Drug Oriented) to patients who refer to Pharmaceutical Care. Pharmaceutical service activities that were originally only focused on managing drugs as commodities have become comprehensive services in the sense of not only managing drugs, but in a broader sense including the implementation of providing information aimed at improving the quality of life of patients [1]. Patient satisfaction is an important element in evaluating the quality of service by measuring the extent to which patients respond after receiving services. With good quality of service, it will create satisfaction for patients [2].

Patient satisfaction in relation to pharmaceutical services can be measured based on five dimensions, namely the dimensions of Reliability, Responsiveness, Assurance, Empathy, and Tangibles. Patient satisfaction is not only from improving physical environmental facilities, but also efforts to provide satisfaction to patients, especially in the process of interaction between patients and officers in providing health services. As stated by Pohan, patient satisfaction is the

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patient's expectation that arises from the actions of health workers as a result of the performance of health services during the process of interacting in an effort to provide services [3].

Hospital is one of the health facilities that provide health services to the community and plays a strategic role in accelerating the improvement of public health. According to Law of the Republic of Indonesia Number 44 of 2009, a hospital is a health service institution that provides comprehensive individual health services that provide inpatient, outpatient and emergency services (Law of the Republic of Indonesia, 2009)

The main focus of a hospital's service attention is patients who visit the hospital because they need health services. Patients who visit the hospital are not only individuals who experience health problems but also as part of a family. The quality of health care services sold to patients is an important part that needs attention. Packaging of services produced is one of the marketing strategies of health service institutions to their users, namely patients and their families. The management must strive to ensure that the service packages offered are sustainable so that certain hospital segments can be maintained or new patients can be created due to word of mouth from previous service users. The superiority of a health service product also depends on the uniqueness of the service package offered, which is truly in accordance with the hopes (expectations) of its patients [4] .

The initial survey conducted by the author on 30 outpatient patients/families who were met during a visit to the Pharmacy Installation of the Regional General Hospital of Central Buton Regency on October 7, 2024 and November 25-29, 2024, using a questionnaire consisting of 10 statements each with the highest score of 40 and the lowest score of 10. Of the 30 respondents, 21 respondents or around 70% considered the quality of pharmaceutical services to be still lacking and 9 respondents or around 30% considered it good. Based on these data, there is a gap between the expected service guideline standards and the reality in the field. There are patient complaints such as the waiting time for prescription services that is quite long beyond the specified time and the lack of Drug Information obtained by patients. Patients also complain that sometimes some prescription drugs are not available when redeeming drugs at the outpatient Pharmacy Installation even though the drugs are needed by the patient and the limited drugs provided. Complaints about the long waiting time and the lack of drugs indicate obstacles in the efficiency of the work process and management in the pharmaceutical service unit. These things can certainly affect the level of patient satisfaction with pharmaceutical services as Saragih said that patient satisfaction is closely related to whether or not the patient's needs are met. If the patient is satisfied with the service received, the patient will come back to need services both for himself and for his family. So it can be concluded that patient satisfaction has a great influence on health service providers [5] . Therefore, this study was conducted to analyze the quality of pharmaceutical services at the Regional General Hospital of Central Buton Regency and its impact on patient satisfaction, in order to provide relevant improvement recommendations.

2. Method

This study uses a quantitative method with a cross-sectional approach. This study was conducted at the Pharmacy Installation of the Regional General Hospital of Central Buton Regency from November to December 2024. Data collection was carried out by filling out a questionnaire. The research sample consisted of 100 respondents with the purposive sampling method. Data analysis was carried out using univariate, bivariate (Chi-Square) and multivariate (Logistic Regression) analysis.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1. Respondent Characteristics

Based on the data in table 1, it can be seen that the characteristics of respondents based on gender at the Pharmacy Installation of Regional General Hospital of Central Buton Regency are dominated by men with 52 respondents (52%). From the characteristics of respondents based on age, the most respondents are 41-50 years old, namely 47 respondents (47%), in terms of their last education, the majority of respondents have a high school background with a total of 63 respondents (63%), while for the frequency of visits, the majority of respondents have visited more than 2 times at the Pharmacy Installation of Regional General Hospital of Central Buton Regency, namely 65 respondents (65%).

Table 1 Distribution of Respondents Based on Respondent Characteristics at the Pharmacy Installation of Regional General Hospital of Central Buton Regency in 2024.

No	Respondent Characteristics		Number (n)	Percent (%)	Total
1.	Gender	Man	52	52	100
		Woman	48	48	
2.	Age	30-40 years old	12	12	100
		41-50 years old	47	47	
		51-60 years old	41	41	
3.	Education	Junior high school	10	10	100
		Senior high school	63	63	
		PT	27	27	
4.	Frequency of Visits	2 times	35	35	100
		> 2 times	65	65	

Source: Primary Data, 2024.

3.2. Bivariate Analysis

Table 2 Relationship between Physical Evidence (Tangible) and Patient Satisfaction at the Pharmacy Installation of Regional General Hospital of Central Buton Regency

Physical Evidence	Patient Satisfaction				Amount		Pvalue
	Less satisfied		Satisfied				
	N	(%)	N	(%)	n	(%)	
Not enough	15	65.2%	8	34.8%	23	100%	0.001
Good	21	27.3%	56	72.7%	77	100%	
Total	36	36 %	64	64%	100	100%	

Source: Processed primary data, 2024

Based on Table 2. Shows the p-value of the Physical Evidence/Tangible variable $0.001 < 0.05$ so it can be concluded that there is a relationship between physical evidence in pharmaceutical services and Outpatient Satisfaction at the Regional General Hospital of Central Buton Regency.

It is known that 56 respondents (72.7%) who considered physical evidence good showed satisfaction with pharmaceutical services. Respondents stated that they were satisfied with the location of the Pharmacy Installation pharmacy which is easy to reach and close to the outpatient clinic so that patients do not have to travel far to fill prescriptions, clear service flow, a fairly clean and comfortable waiting room, sufficient number of seats and equipped with television media. Meanwhile, 21 respondents (27.3%) were less satisfied because of the appearance of pharmacists who often did not wear uniforms during service hours, the waiting room toilets were poorly maintained, and there was no loudspeaker to call the patient's name during service/dispensing of patient medication at the pharmacy installation, causing some patients to sometimes not hear and experience delays in taking the medication they needed.

The results of this study indicate that the physical evidence (tangible) of outpatient pharmaceutical services in general has met patient expectations. This is in line with research conducted by (Akbari VS, 2022) which states that in the Tangible dimension (physical evidence), the quality of outpatient pharmaceutical services is stated to be very good 82% because it is seen from the waiting room which is quite clean and comfortable, sufficient seating, and equipped with a TV so that patients or patient escorts do not get bored while waiting in line for medicine [3]

Another study in line with (Mahendro et.al, 2022) stated that the level of satisfaction in the tangible dimension at the Ndetudora Health Center, most patients said they were very satisfied with the services provided, especially the existing

facilities and infrastructure. Infrastructure that can support the quality of pharmaceutical services is the availability of leaflets or brochures in the waiting room. The availability of reading materials in the waiting room will prevent patients from feeling bored because while waiting, patients can read and add information from the available leaflets or brochures [6]

Table 3 Relationship between Reliability and Patient Satisfaction at the Pharmacy Installation of Regional General Hospital of Central Buton Regency.

Reliability	Patient Satisfaction				Amount		Pvalue
	Less satisfied		Satisfied				
	n	(%)	n	(%)	n	(%)	
Not enough	30	56.6%	23	43.4%	53	100%	0,000
Good	6	12.8%	41	87.2%	47	100%	
Total	36	36 %	64	64%	100	100%	

Source: Processed primary data, 2024

Based on the Chi-Square analysis, the p-value of the Reliability variable is $0.000 < 0.05$, so it can be concluded that there is a relationship between reliability in pharmaceutical services and outpatient satisfaction at the Regional General Hospital of Central Buton Regency.

In the Reliability dimension, the quality of outpatient pharmacy services at the Regional General Hospital of Central Buton Regency was stated to be lacking by 53%. Respondents' assessments that assessed it as lacking were in several aspects such as the availability of drugs which were sometimes not met at the Regional General Hospital of Central Buton Regency pharmacy installation so that patients had to find and buy the drugs they needed outside the Hospital Pharmacy Installation. In addition, the waiting time for preparing and submitting drug prescriptions was also considered less than satisfactory. Meanwhile, 47% of respondents assessed the communication, information and education provided by pharmacy staff regarding patient treatment as good, which was conveyed clearly. Respondents who were satisfied with the reliability dimension reflected that pharmacy staff were skilled in providing information related to treatment to patients.

This is in line with research (Kunaedi, 2022), namely in the Reliability dimension, the quality of outpatient pharmaceutical services regarding officers in providing drug information is stated as good because according to respondents, officers always provide drug information when taking drugs. Meanwhile, the statement on drug availability is stated as not good, this is supported by complaints from several patients when redeeming drugs, sometimes there are some drugs that are out of stock so that patients are advised to buy drugs outside or at other pharmacies [7].

Table 4 Relationship between Responsiveness and Patient Satisfaction at the Pharmacy Installation of Regional General Hospital of Central Buton Regency

Responsiveness	Patient Satisfaction				Amount		Pvalue
	Less satisfied		Satisfied				
	n	(%)	N	(%)	N	(%)	
Not enough	32	58.2%	23	41.8%	55	100%	0,000
Good	4	8.9%	41	91.1%	45	100%	
Total	36	36 %	64	64%	100	100%	

Source: Processed primary data, 2024

Another study that is in line with this was also put forward by (Fadhilah et al, 2020) that the average satisfaction dimension of reliability obtained was lower than the average respondent's expectations, this was caused by the limited number of pharmacists and having to serve many patients who redeemed drugs at the outpatient pharmacy installation so that pharmacists could not provide maximum service to patients [8].

Reliability is seen in the quality of service provided by officers which can be assessed from the knowledge and skills they have, in addition to the mastery of officers in carrying out tasks according to their fields and the expertise of officers in using existing technology. In addition, the accuracy and precision of pharmaceutical services provided also affect the level of satisfaction of patients [6].

Based on the Chi-Square analysis, a p-value of $0.000 < 0.05$ was obtained, so it can be concluded that there is a relationship between Responsiveness in pharmaceutical services and Outpatient Satisfaction at the Regional General Hospital of Central Buton Regency.

The assessment of service quality is seen from the Responsiveness dimension. 45% of respondents stated that the responsiveness assessment was good, seen from the provision of drug information and explanations from pharmacists regarding the use and side effects of drugs to patients properly and clearly. While 55% of respondents gave a poor assessment. This is related to the waiting time when taking drugs at the Pharmacy Installation, most patients considered the waiting time to be quite long. From the results of the researcher's observations, this was caused by the absence of queue numbers for patient prescriptions received at the pharmacy installation, so that officers served patients not based on queue numbers, causing sometimes patients who came earlier to take drugs to get the last service. Also, the limited number of pharmacists so that the service is less than optimal, and tends to be slow.

In line with the research conducted by Humairah Fadilah (2020), the results of the overall responsiveness dimension based on the level of conformity between satisfaction and expectations obtained $\geq 75\%$, which is 91.5%, can be stated that respondents are satisfied but with an average satisfaction that is lower than the average respondent's expectations. This is because the queue of patients who want to redeem drugs at the outpatient pharmacy installation is too long so that pharmacists need time to prepare the drugs and accuracy is needed in doing it. [8].

Waiting time is one of the minimum standards for pharmaceutical services in hospitals. The waiting time for prescription services is the time period from when the patient submits the prescription to the pharmacist until the patient receives the medicine from the pharmacist. According to the Decree of the Minister of Health of the Republic of Indonesia Number 4 of 2019 concerning Minimum Hospital Service Standards, non-compound prescriptions are 15-30 minutes and compound prescriptions are 30-60 minutes [9]

The responsiveness dimension shows a lower average satisfaction compared to the average expectation. Based on the questionnaire answers, it can be seen that there are many respondents who answered disagree or even strongly disagree, this is because patients have to wait in line for a very long time. In line with research (Tosi Rahmadian, 2023) that in responsiveness, outpatients who stated that they were less satisfied were higher in poor responsiveness (83.3%) compared to good (15.7%). Patients stated that the responsiveness of the officers was less good related to the information provided by the officers about the Drugs Received being unclear. Employee communication that is always appropriate when handling patient needs and complaints is very necessary in optimizing services [10]

The way of communication and the attitude of the officers in the pharmacy in providing services will have an impact on the perception of outpatients towards the pharmacy services provided by the officers. The better the communication between the officers in the pharmacy and the outpatients, and accompanied by a good attitude, the more positive the perception of outpatients towards the pharmacy services.

Table 5 Relationship between Assurance and Patient Satisfaction at the Pharmacy Installation of Regional General Hospital of Central Buton Regency

Guarantee	Patient Satisfaction				Amount		Pvalue
	Less satisfied		Satisfied				
	n	(%)	N	(%)	N	(%)	
Not enough	24	54.5%	20	45.5%	44	100%	0.001
Good	12	21.4%	44	78.6%	56	100%	
Total	36	36 %	64	64%	100	100%	

Source: Processed primary data, 2024

Based on the Chi-Square analysis, a p-value of 0.001 <0.05 was obtained, so it can be concluded that there is a relationship between Guarantees in Pharmaceutical Services and Outpatient Satisfaction at the Regional General Hospital of Central Buton Regency.

In the assurance dimension, the quality of outpatient pharmaceutical services was stated as good at 56%. This can be seen from the officer providing the medicine according to the medicine written in the prescription. If there is any ambiguity in the writing of the prescription, the officer will immediately contact the relevant doctor to confirm the prescription given. The drugs received are in good condition and fit for consumption, ensuring that the drugs obtained are correct and will affect the success of the treatment. With this, patient trust and confidence will increase. This refers to the Regulation of the Minister of Health of the Republic of Indonesia Number 72 of 2016 concerning Pharmaceutical Service Standards in Hospitals, which states that pharmaceutical officers must be able to provide quality, effective, efficient and safe services, as well as protect patients from inappropriate drug use.

As many as 44% of respondents considered the assurance dimension to be less than the statement that the drugs written on the prescription are always available in the pharmacy installation. Some patients find that their medicines are sometimes not fully available at the pharmacy. This is in line with research by Aan Kunaedi (2022) that the majority of respondents assessed that patient satisfaction was good or that patients felt satisfied. But there is a question that according to respondents is considered dissatisfied, namely about the availability of drugs. According to respondents, when going to redeem drugs, often the stock of drugs is not available or empty. The availability of drugs is very important because it is one of the factors that affects the quality of service in the hospital. If the stock of drugs is not available, the hospital will be faced with the risk of not meeting the needs of patients [7] .

The results of the same study were also revealed by (Tosi Rahmadian , 2023) that more than half (50.7%) of outpatients stated that the guarantee of officers at the pharmacy was good in providing services. The ability of officers at the pharmacy to communicate well is very important and influences the trust of outpatients. For this reason, a friendly, polite and convincing attitude will influence the confidence of outpatients in the guarantee of the pharmacy's services. The better the guarantee of security provided, the patient will assess the health facility well, because it provides services that are in accordance with the patient's expectations and the patient can be said to be satisfied with the services provided. Therefore, it is expected that officers at the pharmacy will not rush in providing information about the drugs given so that outpatients can understand more clearly about the drugs [10] .

Table 6 Relationship between Empathy and Patient Satisfaction at the Pharmacy Installation of Regional General Hospital of Central Buton Regency

Empathy	Patient Satisfaction				Amount		Pvalue
	Less satisfied		Satisfied				
	n	(%)	N	(%)	n	(%)	
Not enough	17	56.7%	13	43.3%	30	100%	0.007
Good	19	27.1%	51	72.9%	70	100%	
Total	36	36 %	64	64%	100	100%	

Source: Processed primary data, 2024

Based on the Chi-Square analysis, a p-value of 0.007 <0.05 was obtained, so it can be concluded that there is a relationship between Empathy in pharmaceutical services and Outpatient Satisfaction at the Regional General Hospital of Central Buton Regency.

In the empathy dimension, the quality of outpatient pharmaceutical services was stated to be good by 70% of respondents, seen from an emotional perspective, namely officers pay attention and behave well when giving medicine, communicate well and can understand what the patient feels. Empathy is important for health workers because by having a sense of attention and being more responsive to patients, it will speed up the patient's healing time. In line with research conducted by Diki Muhamammad (2020) that patients feel very satisfied with the Empathy dimension which is obtained with an average percentage score of 80.3 % categorized on a Likert scale, namely very satisfied. The researcher's observations at the Sekarwangi Hospital, pharmaceutical services are carried out the same without distinguishing social status, from taking medicine according to the queue number, and understanding patient needs such as when asking and answering questions with patients are carried out in a friendly and polite manner [11] .

This study is also in line with research conducted by (Prafangesta et . Al, 2022) which states that the level of patient satisfaction at RSUD dr. Soediran Mangun Sumarso Wonogiri in the empathy dimension is in the very satisfied category (89.40 %). The highest value is in the indicator of friendly officers when providing services to patients as much as 90.40 % with a very satisfied category. Empathy can be seen from the ability of officers to show concern for what patients need, understand what patients feel and need, and be able to establish good relationships with patients. The assessment of the empathy dimension can be seen in the concern of officers in responding to complaints from patients and their families without distinguishing between patient backgrounds. In addition, officers are also friendly in listening to what patients complain about and patiently explain in language that is easy for patients and families to understand [12] .

The caring and friendly attitude shown by pharmacists to all patients regardless of religion, ethnicity, and social status makes patients feel comfortable. This will have an impact on the level of patient satisfaction where when patients feel comfortable with the services provided, it will indirectly create a desire to return [13] .

Table 7 Relationship between Conformance and Patient Satisfaction at the Pharmacy Installation of Regional General Hospital of Central Buton Regency

Compliance	Patient Satisfaction				Amount		Pvalue
	Less satisfied		Satisfied				
	n	(%)	N	(%)	n	(%)	
Not enough	11	68.8%	5	31.3%	16	100%	0.004
Good	25	29.8%	59	70.2%	84	100%	
Total	36	36 %	64	64%	100	100%	

Source: Processed primary data, 2024

Based on the Chi-Square analysis, a p-value of 0.004 <0.05 was obtained, so it can be concluded that there is a relationship between the suitability of pharmaceutical services and the satisfaction of outpatients at the Regional General Hospital of Central Buton Regency.

From the research results, it was found that out of 84 respondents with good conformity, 59 respondents (70.2 %) were satisfied and 25 respondents (29.8%) were less satisfied. Out of 16 respondents with less assurance, 5 respondents (31.3 %) were satisfied and 11 respondents (68.8%) were less satisfied. The majority of respondents (84%) assessed that the conformance dimension was good or patients were satisfied as seen from the drugs given to patients according to the prescription, officers provided information and counseling about the drugs given such as the name of the drug, the amount of drug, dosage and rules for using the drug, special rules, indications, side effects, contraindications, and expiration dates and others.

This study is in line with research conducted by (Ni Putu Ayu, 2023) that the suitability of the prescription with the formulary has a significant relationship with patient satisfaction with health services. From this statement, it can be concluded that if the prescription is in accordance with the formulary, it can increase patient satisfaction with the services received and can also have a positive impact on the quality of hospital services, conversely, the inconsistency of the prescription with the national formulary will affect the level of satisfaction where patients feel less satisfied or dissatisfied which results in a decrease in the quality of hospital services. Prescriptions that are not in accordance with the national formulary cause prescriptions to be rejected because the drug is not included in the treatment package. Therefore, patients have to spend additional costs to get drugs that meet the recommended dose and duration of therapy. This will burden patients because patients have paid BPJS contributions every month [14]

Regulation of the Minister of Health of the Republic of Indonesia Number 72 of 2016 concerning Standards of Pharmaceutical Services in Hospitals states that officers must be able to provide information about the drugs given and be able to provide counseling to help solve problems faced by patients. Based on this regulation, the characteristics of officer services in providing pharmaceutical services to patients are in accordance with standards. However, some respondents, as many as 16 % , considered that the suitability was still lacking regarding the availability of drugs. The availability of drugs is also regulated by Regulation of the Minister of Health of the Republic of Indonesia Number 72 of 2016 concerning Standards of Pharmaceutical Services in Hospitals, which states that the implementation of pharmaceutical services in hospitals must guarantee the availability of human resources and pharmaceutical supplies (drugs) so that pharmaceutical services run well (Permeances, 2016)

4. Multivariate Analysis

This analysis is to see the influence (relationship) between the independent variables on the dependent variable using the logistic regression analysis type so that the independent variable that most dominantly influences the dependent variable is obtained.

Table 8 The Influence of Physical Evidence (Tangible), Reliability, Responsiveness, Assurance, Empathy and Conformance on Outpatient Satisfaction at the Pharmacy Installation of Regional General Hospital of Central Buton Regency.

Variables	B	Sig.	Exp(B)
Physical Evidence	0.349	0.015	1,417
Reliability	0.544	0.001	1,723
Responsiveness	0.549	0.001	1,731
Guarantee	0.256	0.023	1,291
Empathy	0.281	0.024	1,325
Compliance	0.348	0.023	1,416

Source: Processed primary data, 2024

Based on Table 8, after conducting a logistic regression test, it is known that the variables of Physical Evidence, Reliability, Responsiveness, Assurance, Empathy and Suitability have a positive sig value (p-value) and each with a sig value (p-value) <0.05. This means that the six variables interact with each other to influence Patient Satisfaction at the Pharmacy Installation of Regional General Hospital of Central Buton Regency. Furthermore, to determine the magnitude of the influence of the six variables on Patient Satisfaction which is indicated by the Exp (B) value or also called the Odds Ratio (OR), namely:

- The Physical Evidence (Tangible) variable with an Exp (B) value of 1.417 means that a one unit increase in the Physical Evidence (Tangible) variable has a 41.7% chance of influencing Patient Satisfaction.
- Reliability variable with an Exp (B) value of 1.723 means that a one unit increase in the Reliability variable has a 72.3 % chance of influencing Patient Satisfaction.
- The Responsiveness variable with an Exp (B) value of 1.731 means that a one unit increase in the Responsiveness variable has a 73.1 % chance of influencing Patient Satisfaction.
- Assurance variable with an Exp (B) value of 1.291 means that a one unit increase in the Assurance variable has a 29.1% chance of influencing Patient Satisfaction.
- Empathy variable with an Exp (B) value of 1.325 means that a one unit increase in the Empathy variable has a 32.5% chance of influencing Patient Satisfaction.
- The Conformance variable with an Exp (B) value of 1.416 means that a one unit increase in the Conformance variable has a 41.6 % chance of influencing Patient Satisfaction.

So, it can be concluded that the most dominant variable influencing Patient Satisfaction is Responsiveness with the highest Exp (B) value of 1.731, meaning that respondents who gave their opinion on the importance of Responsiveness have a 73,1% chance of influencing Patient Satisfaction at the Pharmacy Installation of Regional General Hospital of Central Buton Regency in 2024. Physical evidence (Tangible) in pharmaceutical services has an important role in shaping patient satisfaction. Elements such as cleanliness and comfort of pharmacy facilities, neatness and professionalism of the appearance of pharmacy staff, and the strategic location of the pharmacy and proximity to outpatient clinics provide easy access for patients. In addition, the provision of modern supporting equipment and informative educational materials further strengthens the positive impression of service quality. When physical evidence is well managed, patients feel valued and comfortable, so their satisfaction increases. On the other hand, if these aspects are ignored, a negative impression may arise and reduce patient confidence in the service, even though the technical aspects of the service are adequate. Good physical evidence demonstrates the hospital's commitment to quality service. When patients see attention paid to physical details, such as room layout, cleanliness, and provision of modern equipment, they are more likely to believe that the hospital has high standards in all aspects of its service. This creates a sense of satisfaction that is not only momentary but also has long-term impacts, such as increased patient loyalty and positive recommendations to others. Thus, physical evidence plays a strategic role in creating satisfaction and building the reputation of the hospital pharmacy installation.

According to Parasuraman's theory, the tangible dimension functions as real evidence of service quality that cannot always be assessed directly. Patients tend to use physical evidence as an initial benchmark before feeling other aspects, such as reliability or responsiveness of service. Therefore, ensuring that physical evidence in pharmaceutical installations reflects professionalism and high quality is a strategic step to create a satisfying experience. A clean, organized, easily accessible pharmacy installation from the polyclinic, and equipped with modern equipment not only supports smooth operations, but also provides a sense of comfort that contributes to patient trust and loyalty to hospital services.

Reliability in pharmaceutical services in hospitals has a major influence on patient satisfaction. Reliability refers to the ability of a pharmaceutical facility to provide accurate, consistent, and timely services in accordance with patient expectations. For example, fast service in providing medication, accuracy in providing prescriptions, and consistency of information provided by pharmacists are aspects that indicate reliability. When patients feel that the pharmacy can be relied upon to meet their needs without errors or delays, they tend to feel satisfied and confident in the quality of service provided. On the other hand, unreliability such as long waiting times, errors in medications provided, or lack of needed medication supplies, can lead to frustration and dissatisfaction among patients. In the theory of service quality, reliability is one of the main dimensions that affect patient perception of the overall service. Therefore, improving the reliability aspect through staff training, optimizing work processes, and good drug stock management are important steps to ensure patient satisfaction while strengthening the positive image of the hospital.

The responsiveness variable can be very influential compared to other variables in the context of patient satisfaction because it is directly related to the patient's experience during the service process. Patients tend to feel more satisfied when their needs or complaints are handled quickly and effectively. In pharmaceutical services, this includes several aspects, such as speed in providing medication, the ability to answer patient questions clearly and in a timely manner, and responsiveness to problems or concerns that arise during treatment. Speed of service, minimal waiting time, and responsiveness in responding to patient requests or complaints can increase the patient's feeling of being valued and prioritized. In a fast-paced world, patients often want immediate and efficient solutions. If they feel that pharmaceutical personnel are able to provide services that are not only appropriate, but also fast and responsive, they will feel more satisfied and more likely to continue using the service. In addition, responsiveness also strengthens patient trust in the quality of service provided. Patients who feel served quickly and responsively will have a positive perception of the efficiency and professionalism of the health facility, which will increase their loyalty. Therefore, the responsiveness variable can be more influential than other variables because it has a direct impact on the patient experience regarding their comfort and satisfaction in receiving services.

The assurance dimension in pharmaceutical services has a significant influence on patient satisfaction. Assurance includes competence, courtesy, a sense of security, and the ability of pharmaceutical personnel to provide accurate and reliable information. When pharmacists or pharmacy technicians demonstrate in-depth knowledge, communicate clearly, and treat patients with respect, patients feel more confident and comfortable in using the services provided. In addition, the sense of security that arises from professional and responsible service increases positive perceptions of service quality, thereby contributing to higher levels of satisfaction. Therefore, strengthening the assurance dimension is an important factor in improving the overall quality of pharmaceutical services.

The empathy dimension in pharmaceutical services plays an important role in increasing patient satisfaction because it reflects the ability of pharmaceutical personnel to understand the needs, concerns, and conditions of patients personally. Empathy includes individual attention, willingness to listen, and an attitude of concern for the patient's well-being. When pharmacy staff demonstrate empathy, patients feel valued and treated as individuals, not just service users. This creates a positive emotional connection, increases trust, and encourages more effective communication between patients and pharmacists so that patients are more satisfied with the services they receive and tend to be more compliant with recommended therapies, which ultimately results in better health outcomes.

If the empathy dimension in pharmaceutical services is deemed lacking, the impact can be a decrease in patient satisfaction levels. Lack of empathy can make patients feel neglected or treated as mere "service objects," rather than as individuals with unique problems or conditions. This can cause discomfort, reduce trust in pharmaceutical personnel, and hinder effective communication. As a result, patients may feel reluctant to ask questions or express concerns regarding drug therapy, which may ultimately affect their adherence to treatment and overall health outcomes. In the long term, lack of empathy can also damage the image of pharmaceutical services and reduce patient loyalty to the health facility.

The Conformance Dimension looks at the extent to which the characteristics of the pharmaceutical services provided are in accordance with the established pharmaceutical service standards. The conformance variable in pharmaceutical

services has a significant influence on outpatient satisfaction, because it reflects the extent to which the services provided are in accordance with standards, guidelines, and patient expectations. In the context of pharmaceutical services, conformity can be seen from the accuracy of administering drugs according to doctor's prescriptions, the accuracy of information related to drug use, and compliance with established procedures. When services meet expected standards, patients feel more confident and believe that the treatment provided will support their recovery. Conversely, if there is a discrepancy, such as an error in administering drugs or a lack of important information, this can reduce patient satisfaction, increase the risk of non-compliance, and even cause health hazards. Therefore, maintaining appropriateness variables is key to ensuring a safe, reliable, and satisfying service experience for outpatients.

Health facilities, especially pharmaceutical services, are required to implement quality services in the health sector. Quality service can be seen from the level of patient satisfaction. Patient satisfaction is a comprehensive part and quality assurance activity in health services, meaning that patient satisfaction must be an activity that cannot be separated from the quality of health services. The Indonesian Ministry of Health stated that one part of the service that cannot be separated from the hospital is pharmaceutical services. Pharmaceutical services must provide the necessary pharmaceutical supplies, medical devices, and quality and affordable consumables for all levels of society, so that pharmaceutical services must focus on patient care. Pharmaceutical services to patients are carried out directly with full responsibility. This aims to ensure that the pharmaceutical preparations provided are able to achieve therapeutic goals so that the patient's quality of life can be achieved [12]

Patient satisfaction is a comparison between expectations and the reality felt by patients after receiving health services from officers. Patients will feel satisfied if they receive health services that are at least in accordance with their expectations or even more than they expected. The achievement of these patient expectations will have an impact on patient satisfaction with the services provided. Good quality health services are health services that are carried out in accordance with applicable standard operating procedures and professional codes of ethics [15]

5. Conclusion

There is an influence of the quality of pharmaceutical services based on the dimensions of Physical Evidence (Tangible), Reliability, Responsiveness, Assurance, Empathy, and Conformance on the satisfaction of outpatients at the Regional General Hospital of Central Buton Regency. The dimension that has the most significant influence on the satisfaction of outpatients at the Regional General Hospital of Central Buton Regency is Responsiveness.

Compliance with ethical standards

Disclosure of conflict of interest

The authors have no conflict of interest in this research.

Statement of ethical approval

This research has obtained a permit or recommendation from the Health Study Ethics Committee (KEPK) of the Regional Management of the Indonesian Public Health Experts Association (IAKMI) of Southeast Sulawesi Province with Number 274/KEPK-IAKMI/XII/2024.

Statement of informed consent

Informed consent was obtained from all individual participants included in the study.

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